

Review Article**Biofield Energy Signals, Energy Transmission and Neutrinos****Mahendra Kumar Trivedi, T. R. Rama Mohan***

Trivedi Global Inc., Henderson, Nevada, USA

Email address:

publication@trivedieffect.com (T. R. R. Mohan)

*Corresponding author

To cite this article:Mahendra Kumar Trivedi, T. R. Rama Mohan. Biofield Energy Signals, Energy Transmission and Neutrinos. *American Journal of Modern Physics*. Vol. 5, No. 6, 2016, pp. 172-176. doi: 10.11648/j.ajmp.20160506.12**Received:** September 28, 2016; **Accepted:** October 11, 2016; **Published:** November 1, 2016

Abstract: There has been significant data published in peer-reviewed scientific journals about Mr. Mahendra Kumar Trivedi exercising the biofield energy to change the behaviour and characteristics of living organisms including soil, seeds, plants, trees, animals, microbes, and humans, along with non-living materials including metals, ceramics, polymers, chemicals, pharmaceutical compounds and nutraceuticals, etc. This effect of Mr. Trivedi's biofield energy on living beings and non-living materials is referred to as The Trivedi Effect[®]. The changes are attributed to changes at the atomic level and the subatomic level. Changes in atomic/molecular weights are postulated to the changes in atomic mass and atomic charge through possible mediation of neutrinos. The recent discovery of neutrino oscillations seems to give credence to our postulates. This paper discusses briefly about the neutrinos and some of Mr. Trivedi's results and attempts to link these to biofield energy and associated signal transmissions.

Keywords: Biofield Energy, Neutrinos, Neutrino Oscillations, GC-MS, Brain-Computer Interface (BCI)

1. Introduction

A neutrino is perhaps the tiniest quantity of reality ever imagined by a human being. After several efforts, particle physicists have finally obtained a model quite satisfactorily describing the particles of matter and the way they interact [1]. This model, called the "Standard Model", has reduced considerably the number of "elementary particles" [2-5]. According to the Standard Model, 12 particles are the basis of matter: 6 quarks and 6 leptons, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Twelve (12) fundamental particles according to the Standard Model.

Leptons			Quarks		
e^-	μ^-	τ^-	u	c	t
ν_e	ν_μ	ν_τ	d	s	b

Apart from the ν_τ neutrino, all the particles, leptons and quarks have been put into evidence experimentally by the particles accelerators and detectors or bubble chambers or both. To each charged lepton (electron, muon, tau) is

associated a neutral lepton or neutrino (ν_e for the electron, ν_μ for the muon, and ν_τ for the tau). In fact, many important questions concerning the neutrino are still not yet experimentally resolved (Table 2). In general, there are four fundamental interactions between the particles: the strong interaction, the electromagnetic interaction, the weak interaction, and the gravitational interaction [6]. The neutrinos are only concerned with the weak interaction and this allows them to pass through the earth without any deviation or so. At best, they interact only one time over one billion in the huge apparatus built to detect them [7, 8].

Reines and Cowan [9] experiments used a target made of around 400 liters of a mixture of water and cadmium chloride. The anti-neutrino coming from the nuclear reactor interacts with a proton of the target matter, giving a positron and a neutron. The positron annihilates with an electron of the surrounding material, giving two simultaneous photons and the neutron slows down until it is eventually captured by a cadmium nucleus, implying the emission of photons some 15 microseconds after those of the positron annihilation. All

those photons are detected and the 15 microseconds identify the neutrino interaction [10].

In 2015, physics Noble Prize winners Arthur B. McDonald [11] and Takaaki Kajita [12] explained that the neutrinos change identities (change of flavor) which is only possible if the neutrinos possess mass and have the ability to interchange their phase internally from one phase to another (change of flavor). It can be noticed from Tables 2 and 3 that a change of flavor in the neutrinos causes minor changes in their mass by several orders of magnitude [13, 14].

Table 2. Predicted characteristics of neutrinos as compared to electrons, protons, and neutrons.

	Spin	Mass	Magnetic spin
e ⁻			
ν _e	1/2	< 2.8 eV	< 5.8 10 ⁻²⁰ MeV/T
P ⁺			
ν _μ	1/2	< 170 keV or 1.7*10 ⁵ eV	< 4.3 10 ⁻²⁰ MeV/T
n			
ν _τ	1/2	< 18.2 MeV or 1.82*10 ⁷	< 3.1 10 ⁻¹⁷ MeV/T

Table 3. Predicted characteristics of neutrinos [15].

Charged lepton / antiparticle				Neutrino / antineutrino			
Name	Symbol	Electric charge (e)	Mass (MeV/c ²)	Name	Symbol	Electric charge (e)	Mass (MeV/c ²)
Electron / Positron	e ⁻ /e ⁺	-1 / +1	0.511	Electron neutrino / Electron antineutrino	ν _e /ν̄ _e	0	< 0.0000022
Muon	μ ⁻ /μ ⁺	-1 / +1	105.7	Muon neutrino / Muon antineutrino	ν _μ /ν̄ _μ	0	< 0.17
Tau lepton	τ ⁻ /τ ⁺	-1 / +1	1777	Tau neutrino / Tau antineutrino	ν _τ /ν̄ _τ	0	< 15.5

For MeV to kg Conversion, use $E = mc^2$ to convert Joules to kg and then use the fact that 1 MeV is the energy required to move a charge e across a potential difference of 10⁶ volts. Thus 1 MeV is 1.6×10⁻¹⁹×10⁶ Joules.

Therefore

$$m(\text{kg})=10^6 eE(\text{MeV})c^2$$

or

$$m(\text{kg})=1.780 \times 10^{-30} E(\text{MeV})$$

A handy thing to remember is that the electron rest mass is equivalent to 0.511 MeV.

The solar neutrino flux reaching earth is about 65 billion neutrinos, passing through just one square centimeter of area on earth, every second. Thus every second, trillions of neutrinos are passing through the body. Over the course of a lifetime, about 10²³ neutrinos can stream through the body that's almost a trillion of trillions [16]. This in itself is not alarming as neutrinos are neutral and the body is transparent to them [17].

2. Biofield

Electrical currents, along with associated complex and dynamic magnetic fields, are present inside living bodies on many different scales, most likely due to dynamic processes such as heart and brain function, blood and lymph flow, ion transport across cell membranes, and other biologic processes [18]. Biofield is a cumulative effect exerted by these fields of the human body on the surroundings. Typically, it may act directly on molecular structures, changing the conformation of molecules in functionally significant ways as well as may transfer bio-information through energy signals interacting directly with the energy fields of life [19-22]. At the balanced intersection of human and machine adaptation is found the optimally functioning brain-computer interface (BCI) [23]. Experiments are reported of BCI controlling a robotic quadcopter in three-dimensional (3D) physical space using

noninvasive scalp electroencephalogram (EEG), which tracks and records brain wave patterns in human subjects. These experiments indicate that brain waves transmit signals (possibly electromagnetic) that can be received by the receiving brain or receiving electronic instruments. If brain waves are associated with thoughts, then many psychic phenomena can be explained.

3. Mahendra Kumar Trivedi's Experiments Using Biofield Energy (The Trivedi Effect®)

Mr. Trivedi is known to transform the characteristics and behavior of living beings and non-living materials through biofield energy transmitted by his physical presence, as well as long distance through his thought intention. The results of the transformative process of Mr. Trivedi's biofield energy is called The Trivedi Effect®. The details of several scientific investigations and the results in the form of original data have been published in standard, peer-reviewed scientific journals and cited widely [24-27].

Briefly the results indicated that computations using X-ray diffraction on inorganics and organics showed changes in lattice parameters, volume of crystal unit cell, atomic and molecular weights and effective charge on the atom [14]. Mass spectroscopy showed the isotopic abundance of [M+1] ions increased or decreased, thereby suggesting the change in number of neutrons [28-36]. These changes in turn modified the physical characteristics of powders such as particle size, specific surface area (chemical reactivity) density, particle size distribution and thermal behavior etc. [14, 30, 37-39]. The changes in atomic and molecular weights, effective charge on the atom and crystal lattice parameters caused changes in DNA and cell behavior and thus antibiotic susceptibilities [40-43], medicinal and chemical behavior of living beings such as agricultural products [44, 45], fruits

[46], plants [47], medicines and human behavior and characteristics. It was then postulated that these are due to changes in nuclei possibly through intervention of neutrinos by any of the weak reactions [37, 38, 48-51].

The discovery of neutrino oscillations and neutrino mass and magnetic spin changes this picture and in the light of the new information on neutrinos we now explain the biofield experimental results of Trivedi based on the new postulates as follows:

a. The human body as well as brain contains several salt solutions and neutrinos. Based on Reines and Cowan's experiments, it is possible for neutrinos to interact with protons of the salts giving a positron and a neutron. The positron annihilates with an electron of the surrounding material, giving two simultaneous photons and the neutron slows down until it is eventually captured by a metallic nucleus of the salt, causing the emission of photons some 15 microseconds after those of the positron annihilation. The metallic ion gains a neutron. This is proved by Trivedi's experimental results using GC-MS [22, 50].

Thus one of the effects of neutrino interaction with body fluids increases the number of neutrons of the metallic ion of the salt solution. The neutrons can also be decreased by weak interactions effectively increasing protons. The latter pulls the electron cloud in the atom/ion closer to the nucleus, thus decreasing effective surface charge on the atom, affecting the bond energy [52].

b. The neutrino oscillations require energy. This is possible by extraordinary individuals, who can negate all stray thoughts (as in meditation or intense concentration) and focus these in a single intended direction. Often, such individuals in this state emit radiation known to be halos (could be linked to photon emission).

c. The focused thoughts then emit neutral neutrinos from the brain that travel through the biofield and strike the receiver brain and once again the neutrino oscillations take place, giving rise to positive (proton) and negative (electron) signals. These will interact and replicate the sender thought pattern as demonstrated by brain-computer interface (BCI) experiments of LaFleur. K *et al.* [23]. We therefore postulate that thoughts are a focused beam of neutral neutrinos and can change into positive and negative on interacting with a receiver object composed of atoms and ions and replicate the original signals and thought pattern.

d. The neutrinos generated by the thought pattern can create oscillations in the receiver, thus causing subtle changes that alter atomic, molecular, crystalline, cellular, and chemical behavior as demonstrated by Trivedi's experimental results [29].

These explanations are given based on the current state of our knowledge on neutrinos. While the experiments and results are true, further advances in theoretical physics and chemistry of neutrinos are required.

4. Summary

Mahendra Kumar Trivedi is known to transform the

behavior and characteristics of living beings and non-living materials through biofield energy transmitted by his physical presence, as well as long distance through his thought intention. The results of the transformative process of Mr. Trivedi's biofield energy is called The Trivedi Effect[®]. Based on the information available on neutrino oscillations and biofield and brain computer interface (BCI), Mr. Trivedi's experimental results are explained by certain postulates. The neutrino oscillations require energy. This is possible by extraordinary individuals, who can negate all stray thoughts (as in meditation or intense concentration) and focus these in a single intended direction. Often, such individuals in this state emit radiation known to be halos (could be linked to photon emission). The thoughts are thus a focused beam of neutral neutrinos and can change into positive and negative on interacting with a receiver object composed of atoms and ions and replicate the original signals and thought pattern as observed in BCI and other psychic phenomena. The effect of neutrino interaction with body fluids increases the number of neutrons of the metallic ion of the salt solution. Sometimes, the neutrons can also be decreased by weak interactions effectively increasing protons. The latter pulls the electron cloud in the atom/ion closer to the nucleus, thus decreasing effective surface charge on the atom affecting the bond energy. The neutrinos generated by the thought pattern can create oscillations in the receiver, thus causing subtle changes that alter atomic, molecular, crystalline, cellular, and chemical behavior as demonstrated by Trivedi's experimental results.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Trivedi Global, Inc. and the various scientists and coauthors of different publications.

References

- [1] Kajita T (2010) Atmospheric neutrinos and discovery of neutrino oscillations. Proceedings of the Japan Academy Series B, Physical and Biological Sciences 86 (4): 303-321.
- [2] Langacker P, Liu J (1992) Standard model contributions to the neutrino index of refraction in the early Universe. Phys Rev D Part Fields 46 (10): 4140-4160.
- [3] Chapline G (2006) Quantum phase transitions and event horizons: Condensed matter analogies. International Journal of Modern Physics B 20: 2647-2650.
- [4] Clayton D (2003) Handbook of Isotopes in the Cosmos: Hydrogen to Gallium, Cambridge University Press, New York.
- [5] Qian Y-Z, Vogel P, Wasserburg GJ (1999) Neutrino fluence after r-process freeze-out and abundances of Te isotopes in presolar diamonds. Astrophys J 513: 956-960.
- [6] Thurner S, Fuchs B (2015) Physical forces between humans and how humans attract and repel each other based on their social interactions in an online world. Xia C-Y, ed. PLoS ONE 10 (7): e0133185.

- [7] Besson D, Cowen D, Selen M, Wiebusch C. Neutrinos (1999) Proceedings of the national academy of sciences of the united states of America 96 (25): 14201-14202.
- [8] Wu CS, Ambler E, Hayward RW, Hoppes DD, Hudson RP (1957) Experimental test of parity conservation in beta decay. Phys Rev 105: 1413.
- [9] Reines F, Clyde L, Cowan Jr., (1956) The neutrino. Nature 178: 446.
- [10] Cowan CL (1955) New version of free neutrino experiment. 2924 of AECU, U. S. Atomic Energy Commission
- [11] McDonald, AB (2015) The sudbury neutrino observatory: Observation of flavor change for solar neutrinos: Lecture slides Nobel Lecture, Aula Magna, Stockholm University.
- [12] Kajita, T (2015) Discovery of atmospheric neutrino oscillations: lecture slides, Nobel lecture, Aula Magna, Stockholm University.
- [13] Vogel P, Wen LJ, Zhang C (2015) Neutrino oscillation studies with reactors. Nature Communications 6: 6935.
- [14] Balantekin AB (2013) Neutrinos and rare isotopes Journal of Physics: Conference Series 445 012022.
- [15] Amsler C, Doser M, Antonelli M, Asner DM, Babu KS, *et al.* (2008). Review of Particle Physics. Physics Letters B 667: 1.
- [16] Rott C, Taketa A, Bose D (2015) Spectrometry of the earth using neutrino oscillations. Scientific reports 5: 15225.
- [17] Domogatskii GV, Nadezhin DK (1978) Neutrino production of bypassed isotopes, and the possible role of neutrinos in nucleosynthesis. Astron Zh 55: 516-530.
- [18] Rubik B (1994) Bioelectromagnetics applications in medicine. Alternative medicine: expanding medical horizons: a report to the National Institutes of Health on alternative medical systems and practices in the United States (NIH publication no. 94-066). US Government Printing Office, Washington DC, USA.
- [19] Trivedi MK, Nayak G, Patil S, Tallapragada RM, Latiyal O (2015) Studies of the atomic and crystalline characteristics of ceramic oxide nano powders after bio field treatment. Ind Eng Manage 4: 161.
- [20] Rubik B, Muehsam D, Hammerschlag R, Jain S (2015) Biofield science and healing: history, terminology, and concepts. Global advances in health and medicine 4 (Suppl): 8-14.
- [21] Becker RO, Selden G (1985) The body electric: Electromagnetism and the foundation of life, New York City, William Morrow and Company.
- [22] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Tallapragada RM (2013) Effect of bio field treatment on the physical and thermal characteristics of silicon, tin and lead powders. J Material Sci Eng 2: 125.
- [23] LaFleur K, Cassidy K, Doud A, Shades K, Rogin E (2013) Quadcopter control in three-dimensional space using a noninvasive motor imagery-based brain-computer interface. J Neural Eng 10 (4).
- [24] Yount G, Patil S, Dave U, Alves-dos-Santos L, Gon K, Arauz R, Rachlin K (2013) Evaluation of biofield treatment dose and distance in a model of cancer cell death. Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine 19 (2): 124-127.
- [25] Trivedi MK., Tallapragada RR (2009) Effect of superconsciousness external energy on atomic, crystalline and powder characteristics of carbon allotrope powders. Materials Research Innovations 13 (4) 473-480.
- [26] Trivedi MK, Tallapragada RM (2008) A transcendental to changing metal powder characteristics. Metal Powder Report 63 (9): 22-28, 31.
- [27] Dabhade, VV, Rama Mohan TR, Trivedi MK (2009) Effect of external energy on the atomic, crystalline, and powder characteristics of antimony and bismuth powders. Bulletin of Materials Science 32 (5): 471-479.
- [28] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Sethi KK, Jana S (2016) Isotopic abundance ratio analysis of biofield energy treated indole using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Science Journal of Chemistry 4: 41-48.
- [29] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Panda P, Jana S (2016) Evaluation of the isotopic abundance ratio in biofield energy treated resorcinol using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry technique. Pharm Anal Acta 7: 481.
- [30] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Sethi KK, Jana S (2016) Determination of isotopic abundance ratio of biofield energy treated 1,4-dichlorobenzene using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Modern Chemistry 4: 30-37.
- [31] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Panda P, Jana S (2016) Gas chromatography-mass spectrometric analysis of isotopic abundance of ^{13}C , ^2H , and ^{18}O in biofield energy treated p-tertiary butylphenol (PTBP). American Journal of Chemical Engineering 4: 78-86.
- [32] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Sethi KK, Jana S (2016) Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry based isotopic abundance ratio analysis of biofield energy treated methyl-2-naphthylether (Nerolin), American Journal of Physical Chemistry 5: 80-86.
- [33] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Panda P, Jana S (2016) Isotopic abundance ratio analysis of 1,2,3-trimethoxybenzene (TMB) after biofield energy treatment (The Trivedi Effect[®]) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, American Journal of Applied Chemistry 4: 132-140.
- [34] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Sethi KK, Jana S (2016) Evaluation of isotopic abundance ratio in biofield energy treated nitrophenol derivatives using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. American Journal of Chemical Engineering 4: 68-77.
- [35] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Panda P, Jana S (2016) Determination of isotopic abundance of $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ or $^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ and $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ in biofield energy treated 1-chloro-3-nitrobenzene (3-CNB) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Science Journal of Analytical Chemistry 4: 42-51.
- [36] Trivedi MK, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Panda P, Jana S (2016) Mass spectrometric analysis of isotopic abundance ratio in biofield energy treated thymol. Frontiers in Applied Chemistry 1: 1-8.
- [37] Trivedi MK, Tallapragada RM, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Latiyal O, Jana S (2015) Characterization of physical, thermal and structural properties of chromium (VI) oxide powder: impact of biofield treatment. J Powder Metall Min 4: 128.

- [38] Trivedi MK, Tallapragada RM, Branton, A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Latiyal O, Jana S (2015) The potential impact of biofield energy treatment on the atomic and physical properties of antimony tin oxide nanopowder. *American Journal of Optics and Photonics* 3 (6): 123-128.
- [39] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Shettigar H, Singh R, Jana S (2015) An impact of biofield treatment on spectroscopic characterization of pharmaceutical compounds. *Mod Chem Appl* 3: 159.
- [40] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Shettigar H, Gangwar M, Jana S (2015) Antimicrobial sensitivity pattern of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* after biofield treatment. *J Infect Dis Ther* 3: 222.
- [41] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Shettigar H, Bairwa K, Jana S (2015) Phenotypic and biotypic characterization of *Klebsiella oxytoca*: An impact of biofield treatment. *J Microb Biochem Technol* 7: 203-206.
- [42] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Shettigar H, Gangwar M, Jana S (2015) An effect of biofield treatment on multidrug-resistant *Burkholderia cepacia*: A multihost pathogen. *J Trop Dis* 3: 167.
- [43] Patil SA, Nayak GB, Barve SS, Tembe RP, Khan RR (2012) Impact of biofield treatment on growth and anatomical characteristics of *Pogostemon cablin* (Benth.). *Biotechnology* 11: 154-162.
- [44] Sances F, Flora E, Patil S, Spence A, Shinde V (2013) Impact of biofield treatment on ginseng and organic blueberry yield. *Agrivita J Agric Sci* 35: 22-29.
- [45] Lenssen AW (2013) Biofield and fungicide seed treatment influences on soybean productivity, seed quality and weed community. *Agricultural Journal* 83: 138-143.
- [46] Trivedi MK, Branton, A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Mondal SC, Jana S (2015) Morphological characterization, quality, yield and DNA fingerprinting of biofield energy treated alphonso mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Journal of Food and Nutrition Sciences*. 3 (6): 245-250.
- [47] Nayak G, Altekar N (2015) Effect of biofield treatment on plant growth and adaptation. *J Environ Health Sci* 1: 1-9.
- [48] Trivedi MK, Nayak G, Patil S, Tallapragada RM, Latiyal O, Jana S (2015) An evaluation of biofield treatment on thermal, physical and structural properties of cadmium powder. *J Thermodyn Catal* 6: 147.
- [49] Trivedi MK, Nayak G, Patil S, Tallapragada RM, Latiyal O (2015) Impact of biofield treatment on physical, structural and spectral properties of antimony sulfide. *Ind Eng Manage* 4: 165.
- [50] Trivedi MK, Patil S, Nayak G, Jana S, Latiyal O (2015) Influence of biofield treatment on physical, structural and spectral properties of boron nitride. *J Material Sci Eng* 4: 181.
- [51] Trivedi MK, Tallapragada RM, Branton A, Trivedi D, Nayak G, Latiyal O, Jana S (2015) Characterization of physical and structural properties of aluminium carbide powder: Impact of biofield treatment. *J Aeronaut Aerospace Eng* 4: 142.
- [52] Mohapatra RN (1999) Sterile neutrinos: Phenomenology and theory. *AIP Conf Proc* 478, 440.